

Determination of 4-S-Benzyl-1-Parachlorophenyl-5-Phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret in Acetone

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Determination of 4-S-Benzyl-1-Parachlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) in acetone medium has been carried out by enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations, using tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hydroxide, potassium tertiary butoxide and alcoholic potassium hydroxide as titrants. Concentration range for determination of BPPTB was found to be 0.5 to 8.0 mg for enthalpimetric, 0.5 to 7.0 mg for conductometric and 0.5 to 8.0 mg for potentiometric titrations. Potentiometric titrations gave the best results while enthalpimetric titrations are recommended for simplicity and quickness.

4-S-BENZYL-1-Parachlorophenyl-5-Phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) has been recently used in this laboratory for the solvent extraction studies of transition metals¹, thin layer chromatography of metal chelates² and in the structural studies of metal chelates³. Looking into its analytical importance, it was thought worthwhile to develop a suitable method for determination of BPPTB in micro-quantities. In the present paper different methods like enthalpimetric titration, conductometric titration and potentiometric titration, have been used to determine the optimum conditions for quantitative estimation of BPPTB.

Experimental

All chemicals used were A.R. Grade. BPPTB was synthesised and recrystallised by the known method⁴. Acetone was purified and made anhydrous⁵ by keeping it over KMnO_4 for 2 days and then over fused calcium chloride for 2 days. It was then distilled at 56° . Tetra-*n*-butyl-ammonium hydroxide (TBuNH_4OH), Potassium tertiary butoxide (tert. BuOK) and alcoholic potassium hydroxide (Alc.KOH) were prepared and preserved as reported previously⁶.

Instruments and Apparatus :

Direct reading conductometer with C. C. -01 Elico type conductivity cell (cell constant 0.481) was used for conductometric titration. The cell was conditioned by keeping it in anhydrous acetone for 24 hours before titration.

Direct reading potentiometer was used for potentiometric titrations. Calomel electrode, prepared with Hg/HgCl_2 satd. KCl in methyl alcohol

was used as reference electrode and pure aluminium wire (99.99%) of 1 mm diameter was used as an indicator electrode. Small portion of aluminium wire (about 2 mm) was cut off by sharp edge just before each titration.

Procedure :

All titrations were carried in nitrogen atmosphere. Methods for enthalpimetric, conductometric and potentiometric titrations were necessarily the same as reported in our previous communication⁶. End points were always determined graphically.

Results and Discussion

(1) *Choice of Proper Titrant :*

Titration curves for enthalpimetric titration of BPPTB by TBuNH_4OH (curve I), tert. BuOK (Curve II) and Alc. KOH (Curve III) are shown in Fig. 1. The end points are indicated by sudden break in the curve accompanied by sharp rise in temperature. Titration curves for conductometric titrations (Fig. 2) did not show sharp break, but the end points could be determined by extrapolation. However errors in estimation were comparatively large.

Potentiometric titration curves (Fig. 3) show sharp rise in potential at the end point. The end points were determined by differential method to get accurate results.

Comparison of the results obtained by three different methods for TBuNH_4OH , tert. BuOK and Alc. KOH (Table 1) show that Alc. KOH is the most suitable titrant for estimation of BPPTB.

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Fig. 1. Enthalpimetric Titrations of BPPTB
I— TBuNH_4OH
II— tert. BuOK
III— Alc. KOH

Fig. 2. Conductometric Titrations of BPPTB
I— TBuNH_4OH
II— tert. BuOK
III— Alc. KOH

Fig. 3. Potentiometric Titrations of BPPTB
I— TBuNH_4OH
II— tert. BuOK
III— Alc. KOH

Hence Alc. KOH was used as a titrant for further experiments.

TABLE 2—ENTHALPIMETRIC TITRATIONS OF 4-S-BENZYL-1-PARACHLOROPHENYL-2,4-ISODITHIOBIURET (BPPTB)

Effect of dilution					
Solvent-Acetone			Titrant-Alc. KOH		
No.	Vol. of soln taken	Vol. of acetone added	Wt. of BPPTB titrated	Wt found	%error
	ml	ml	mg	mg	
1.	5.0	0.0	2.994	3.011	+0.6
2.	5.0	1.0	2.994	3.011	+0.6
3.	5.0	2.0	2.994	2.968	-0.9
4.	5.0	3.0	2.994	2.982	-0.4
5.	5.0	4.0	2.994	3.011	+0.6
6.	5.0	5.0	2.994	2.968	-0.9
7.	5.0	6.0	2.994	2.968	-0.9

TABLE 1—TITRATIONS OF 4-S-BENZYL-1-PARACHLOROPHENYL-5-PHENYL-2,4-ISODITHIOBIURET (BPPTB)

Effect of nature of titrant

No.	Titrant	Solvent-Acetone			Solvent-Acetone			Solvent-Acetone		
		Enthalpimetric Titration			Conductometric Titration			Potentiometric Titration		
		Wt. of BPPTB taken	Wt. found	%error	Wt. of BPPTB taken	Wt. found	%error	Wt. of BPPTB taken	Wt. found	%error
	mg	mg		mg	mg		mg	mg		
1.	TBuNH_4OH	5.000	4.533	-9.3	4.998	4.017	-19.6	5.040	4.970	-1.4
2.	tert. BuOK	5.000	4.637	-7.3	4.998	4.017	-19.6	5.040	4.910	-2.6
3.	Alc. KOH	5.000	4.983	-0.3	4.998	4.820	-3.6	5.040	5.008	-0.6

TABLE 3—TITRATIONS OF 4-S-BENZYL-1-PARACHLOROPHENYL-2,4-ISODITHIOBIURET (BPPTB)

No.	Solvent-Acetone			Effect of Concentration of solute		Titrant-Alc. KOH			
	Vol. of soln taken	Vol. of acetone added	Wt. of BPPTB titrated	Enthalpimetric titrations		Conductometric titrations		Potentiometric titrations	
	ml	ml	mg	Wt. found mg	%error	Wt. found mg	%error	Wt. found mg	%error
1.	0.5	49.5	0.2495	0.043	—	0.0863	—	0.0971	—
2.	1.0	49.0	0.499	0.4962	-0.6	0.5081	+1.8	0.4965	-0.5
3.	2.0	48.0	0.998	1.010	+1.2	0.9814	-1.7	0.9930	-0.5
4.	4.0	46.0	1.996	1.978	-0.9	1.986	-0.5	1.982	-0.7
5.	6.0	44.0	2.994	3.011	+0.6	2.966	-0.9	2.979	-0.5
6.	8.0	42.0	3.992	4.000	+0.2	3.993	0.0	3.989	-0.1
7.	10.0	40.0	4.990	4.947	-0.9	4.901	-0.9	4.952	-0.8
8.	12.0	38.0	5.988	5.907	-1.3	5.882	-1.9	5.972	-0.3
9.	14.0	36.0	6.986	6.923	-0.9	6.865	-1.7	6.943	-0.6
10.	16.0	34.0	7.984	7.843	-1.8	7.728	-3.2	7.917	-0.8
11.	18.0	32.0	8.982	8.604	-4.2	8.592	-4.3	8.713	-3.0
12.	20.0	30.0	9.980	9.450	-5.3	9.520	-4.6	9.585	-4.0

(2) Effect of dilution :

Effect of dilution was studied by choosing a particular wt. (3 mg) of BPPTB and enthalpimetric titrations were performed using different volumes of acetone under identical conditions (Table 2). From the results it seems that volume of solvent does not have any noticeable effect.

(3) Effect of concentration of the solute :

Stock solution containing 4.99 mg of BPPTB per ml was prepared and different volumes of this solution (0.5 to 20.0 ml) were diluted to 50 ml to get the solutions of different concentrations. 5 ml of each of these solutions were separately titrated enthalpimetrically, conductometrically and potentiometrically and the results (Table 3) were compared.

It is observed from Table 3 that BPPTB can be quantitatively estimated between 0.5 mg to 8.0 mg by enthalpimetric titrations. Beyond these limits the percentage error becomes appreciable. Conductometric titrations also gave good results for 0.5 to 7.0 mg of BPPTB, but the percentage errors were relatively large.

Potentiometric titrations were found to yield best results amongst the three methods. Errors in estimation were found to be minimum (usually less than 1.0%) and the method can estimate 0.5 to 8.0 mg BPPTB accurately under the experimental conditions. However, enthalpimetric method surpasses

the potentiometric method in simplicity and fastness and hence is recommended for quick estimation of BPPTB.

Standard and mean deviations :

Standard and mean deviations for titrations of BPPTB with Alc. KOH were found to be 0.45 and 0.06 for enthalpimetric titrations, 0.04 and 0.81 for conductometric titrations, and 0.03 and 0.31 for potentiometric titrations.

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